

Decentralized exchanges: a study on the impact of security risks on the adoption of decentralized finance

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the quick development of blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies had an impact on the financial industry by creating a new crypto economy. The upcoming generation of decentralized applications has appeared due to smart contracts. DEX's provide many advantages in comparison to centralized exchanges. However, they also bring several security risks. In this paper the focus is on the impact of security risks on the trust in decentralized finance (DeFi) and DEX's, and how security risks and trust impact DeFi adoption. This research discusses several security risks and conducts an empirical study (surveys) to measure the trust in DEX's and DeFi. Additionally, secondary data is researched to form the empirical study and to better understand the research subjects. The results are that the security risks negatively impact the trust in DEX's which negatively affects the adoption of DeFi.

Keywords

FinTech, DeFi, decentralized exchange, smart contracts, blockchain

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the technical term Financial technology (FinTech) has emerged, it is considered a unique taxonomy that primarily describes the broad operating financial technology sector of a company or organization that is primarily concerned with improving the quality of services through the use of information technology (IT) applications (Gai et al., 2018). According to an industry report, the value of investments in Fintech firms have grown by 75% in 2015 to USD 22.3 billion compared to the previous year (Skan et al., 2016). Arner et al. (2015, p.1) describe the evolution of Fintech development as an ongoing process "during which finance and technology have evolved together".

Decentralized finance

FinTech still raises concerns about centralization, such as dictatorship, data monopoly, data tampering, and user privacy issues (Renduchintala et al., 2022). This study will look into the most practical decentralized solution which is Decentralized finance (DeFi). According to research from Zetsche et al., (2020) DeFi is "the decentralized provision of financial services through a mix of infrastructure, markets, technology, methods, and applications" (2020). DeFi uses public blockchain networks to conduct transactions without having to rely on centralized service providers such as custodians, central clearinghouses, or escrow agents. Instead, these roles are assumed by so-called smart contracts.

Smart contracts

A smart contract is a programmable contract that allows two counterparties to set the terms of a transaction without trusting another third party to enforce it. Whenever a certain condition is met, the smart contract executes the action according to the program. Multiple smart contracts are combined to operate with each other, which would be known as a decentralized application (Dapp) to fulfill more complex processes and computations (Lau et al., 2021).

Decentralized exchange

The boom in the cryptocurrency ecosystem is driving the demand for digital asset trading platforms. Cryptocurrency exchanges can be divided into two types: centralized exchanges (CEX's) and decentralized exchanges (DEX's). CEX's require a central institution as an intermediary to complete cryptocurrency transactions between its users (Xia et al., 2020). Since users have no ownership of the exchange's assets, there are still many risks. In 2021, more than \$1.81 billion worth of cryptocurrencies were hacked on these exchanges (Kim Graur et al.,

2022). DEX's facilitate free transactions and eliminate potential security and privacy issues. It will allow users to trade cryptocurrencies without transferring custody of the cryptocurrencies to intermediaries. On the DEX's any user can create trading pairs and let other users use them. However, some users abuse this freedom to commit fraud by misusing security risks that come with DEX's (Cernera et al., 2022).

Trust has become more significant in many industries (Kantsperger & Kunz, 2010). Research from Bahmanziari et al., (2016) states that trust is an important component in technology acceptance and adoption. Some authors state that "relationship marketing is built on the foundation of trust" (Berry, 2000, p. 242) and that "trust is central to successful relationship marketing" (Morgan and Hunt, 1994, p. 22). Therefore, trust is acknowledged as an important mediating variable in the service relationship (Ganesan, 1994; Palmatier et al., 2006).

Considering that the DeFi space is exposed to more untrustworthy services than centralized finance it is expected that the need for trust in service has less impact in DeFi than in CeFi. Therefore the goal of this study is to explore the impact of the security risks of DEX on the trust in DEX and how this affects the trust and adoption of DeFi.

Academic relevance

DeFi is something that has potential to change the financial system as it is known, therefore researching the impact of certain challenges is necessary to promote further DeFi adoption. There is no research on this topic and it can be a valuable contribution to the academic world.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Due to the rapid development of blockchain, blockchain can be applied in various areas such as Education, Finance, Governance, Healthcare, Industry, the Internet of Things (IoT), Supply chain management, e-voting, Privacy, and Security (Sanjay, Srinivas, Madhu & Parikh, 2021). This research will be focusing on the finance area in blockchains, specifically, on the impact of security risks of decentralized finance on the trust and usage of decentralized exchanges and how this affects the adoption of decentralized finance. Existing literature shows that decentralized finance facilitates several security risks that impact mass adoption (Vinella & Jin, 2022). Next to this, existing literature also shows several ways to overcome the security risks presented. However, the impact of these challenges (e.g., rate of scam tokens) on the trustworthiness of DEX's are not yet

researched. Next to this, research also lacks to show how the loss of trustworthiness of DEX's impedes the adoption of decentralized finance.

Knowledge gap

The deficiencies of the current research conducted on decentralized finance results in a knowledge gap. With security and scalability being the two major challenges decentralized finance faces (Amler et al., 2021), a possibility exists that the security risks affect the trustworthiness of decentralized exchanges. Trustworthiness is taken into consideration because the main reaction due to cyber criminality is a lack of trust (Garg, Afroz, Overdorf & Greenstadt, 2015). Next to this, there is an expectation that the lack of trust in these decentralized exchanges contributes to the impediment to the adoption of decentralized finance in the mainstream world. This research will not focus on how these security risks can be prevented, rather, the focus is on how these challenges contribute to the adoption of the decentralized finance ecosystem. The knowledge gap will be further explained by defining the security risks this research will be focussing on.

Scams

Xia et al., (2022) identified over 10.000 scam tokens and pools in total (which is a lower-bound) on Uniswap alone (An DEX on the Ethereum blockchain), meaning that roughly 50% of tokens listed on Uniswap are scam tokens. This research will focus on Rug Pulls (Xia et al., 2022), High Yield Investment Programs (Vasek & Moore, 2015), Smart Contract traps, and Pump-And-Dump Schemes (Xia et al., 2022). There is a necessity to research these types of scams. These scams are risks that exist for every DeFi user. It is important to research the impact of these scams on the trust of the users in DEXs, since increasing the users is connected to increasing the adoption of DeFi

Smart contract vulnerabilities

DeFi products are built upon smart contracts dealing directly or indirectly with user funds. Applications with more locked assets are more attractive to attack (Amler et al., 2021). Due to the immutability property of a blockchain, developers cannot modify the smart contract even though there is a vulnerability that may cause financial losses (Tantikul & Ngamsuriyaroj, 2020). There are several types of vulnerabilities regarding smart contracts. For example, Code exploits, Flash loans, and Security breaches. This research will be considering these vulnerabilities into consideration when looking at the impact of trust.

RESEARCH QUESTION

Based on the knowledge gap established in the previous chapter, the following problem statement is formulated:

“What is the impact of security risks on the trust of Decentralized exchanges, and how does this affect the adoption of Decentralized finance?”

To answer the problem statement research is needed on the number of security risks, and the impact of security risks on the adoption of DeFi by looking at the DEX usage. The first question is formulated to give more insight into the security risks of DeFi. The second question is to gain more insight into how, and to what extent trust can impact a service provider. The third question is to elaborate on the consequences of these scam tokens in the DEX space. The two other theoretical questions are formulated to give a relation between the scam tokens and the adoption of decentralized finance.

- What is the current rate of security risks in DeFi?
- What is the impact of trust on a service?
- To what extent do security risks lower the trust in decentralized exchanges?
- What are the consequences/effects of the security risks on decentralized exchanges?
- How do the security risks affect decentralized exchange usage?
- What is the impact of the amount/increase of security risk on the adoption of DeFi?

Conceptual model

The term DeFi means decentralized finance and is defined as financial services that operate on a public permissionless blockchain (Meegan & Koens, 2021)

The term decentralized exchange or DEX generally refers to distributed ledger protocols and applications that enable users to transact cryptocurrencies without the need to trust a centralized entity to be an intermediary for the trade or a custodian for their cryptocurrencies (Lin, 2019).

When saying “trust in something” or being trustworthy, it implicitly means that the probability that there will be an action that is beneficial or at least not detrimental is high enough to consider engaging in some form of cooperation with something or someone (Gambetta, 2000) In this study the variabel trust or trustworthiness is in service providers and is used to measure the trust in DEX’s, and DeFi, and the impact it has on the adoption of DeFi.

In this research, the increase in security risks on DEX platforms is the independent variable

while the adoption of DeFi is the dependent variable. The trust in DEX platforms acts as a partial mediator between the independent and dependent variables. The relationship between these two variables is illustrated in figure 1. conceptual model.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Hypotheses

Based on the previous chapter’s conceptual model the following hypotheses have been formulated accordingly:

H1: The amount/increase of security risks on Decentralized exchange platforms has a negative effect on adoption of decentralized finance.

H2: The trust in decentralized exchanges can influence the adoption of DeFi.

H3: The increase of security risks has a negative effect on the trust in decentralized exchanges.

METHOD

To include multiple viewpoints, this study uses mixed methods of data collection method. This means a combination of qualitative, quantitative and secondary data is used. For the exploratory part of the research qualitative data is used, the focus of this study was to examine whether security risks have an impact on the trust and usage of decentralized exchanges and how this affects the adoption of decentralized finance. Due to the exploratory nature of this part Research, Theoretical Inductive Methods Use development (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Quantitative data

Quantitative data is used to measure the rise of security risks and the impact it has on DEX’s. The quantitative data is obtained by the organization chain analysis. The use of quantitative data allows for the generalization of the results and uses a deductive approach to theory development as it allows for generalizations of the results (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016). Furthermore, to get a better understanding of the research subject and to create a foundation for qualitative data secondary data is used. Quantitative data is obtained from data provided by chain analysis and surveys. The study is undertaken with data that is gathered one time, which makes it cross-sectional

(Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Secondary data

Additionally, secondary data is used to better understand research subjects. Secondary data are data that have been collected by others for another purpose than the purpose of the current study (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). To ensure that the secondary data are valid criteria is used to select the articles and data. Secondary data that contain valuable information but doesn't correspond with all the criteria will still be used, this is because they excel in other criteria. The selected criteria are:

- Reputable researcher (H-index>10)
- On-chain analysis
- Peer reviewed
- Academic journal
- More than 10 citations

Qualitative data

Qualitative data is data in the form of words. Structured interviews will be used to collect the data. Knowledge about the DEX, DEX security risks and DeFi is possessed by a limited number of experts and the nature of the subject is complex. To select the participants for the interviews, judgment sampling was used based on their knowledge of either DeFi, DEX, and security risks, or a combination of these topics. For this study, the three steps in qualitative data analysis based on the work of Miles and Huberman (1994) will be used. The first step is the reduction of data through coding and categorization. Codes are labels given to units of the text which are later grouped and turned into categories. The second step is to display the reduced data in an organized, condensed manner. And the last step is to conclude to answer the research questions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Survey research

For the sample size for the survey quota sampling and convenience is used. Quota sampling is a method where the selected sample group represents some specific characteristics of the population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). With convenience sampling information is collected from readily available members of the population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The characteristics are people with knowledge about DEX's, the security risks of DEX's, or DeFi. In this research, the sample group consists of students that finished the minor "Blockchain Technology & Cryptocurrencies: a deep dive", teachers at The Hague University of Applied Sciences, and regular civilians. For the regular people, convenience

sampling will be used to measure if there is a difference between people that are not and that are familiar with DeFi.

To conduct the surveys Google forms will be used and sent to the sample groups. To check if the variables are reliable Cronbach's alpha will be calculated. To analyze the variables simple linear regression will be used with the use of SPSS.

RESULTS

To find out to what extent the security risks influence the trust of the user in decentralized exchanges, it is important to analyze the current rate of the security risks in DeFi. In a recently published crypto crime report (Chain analysis, 2022), it is shown that the rise of DeFi has led to new opportunities in crypto crime, the two categories that stand out because of their growth are stolen funds and, to a lesser degree, scams. Stolen funds show that in comparison to 2020, the total value stolen from DeFi platforms in 2021 rose 1330%. With 2.3 billion dollars stolen in total, it is shown that code exploits have the biggest share of the total value stolen. When looking at the scams, there is a total of \$7.7 billion worth of cryptocurrency taken from victims worldwide. This represents a rise of 81% compared to 2020, with the report stating that DEX's, among other platforms, are especially vulnerable.

Scams

A rug pull is a kind of scam where developers abandon a project and take their investors' money. The purpose of performing rug pull scams is to fool the victims to invest in the scam tokens they created and then drain the money from the pools (Xia et al., 2022). When looking at the crypto crime report (Chain analysis, 2022), it becomes clear that rug pulls account for 37% of all cryptocurrency scam revenue in 2021, in comparison to 2020 which counted 1%. It is also stated that rug pulls are most commonly seen in DeFi. (Chain analysis, 2022). Many DEX's adopt the same similar trading mechanism, called the Automated Market Makers (AMMs). Due to these similarities attackers can easily create pools of scam tokens on multiple different DEX's (Xia et al., 2022). Due to the number of rug pulls, this research characterizes rug pulls as a single category.

Looking at how chain analysis categorizes High-Yield-investment programs, smart contract traps, and Pump-and-Dump schemes, these types of scams are accountable for 63% of all of the cryptocurrency crime revenue. An aspect to note is that this research does not take any other scam type into account. This means that the actual percentage of these scams could be lower.

Smart contract vulnerabilities

Cybercriminals, who can analyze the smart contract scripts for vulnerabilities and plan exploits, are accountable for more than 54.98% of the total value stolen across all services, and examining only hacks on DeFi platforms this figure increases to 69.3% (Chain analysis, 2022). Due to these percentages, smart contract vulnerabilities are a focal point in this research. Code audits can be a solution to these acts, however Chain analysis, (2022) states that these audits are not infallible. The two potential shortcomings of code audits are:

- They do not patch all smart contract vulnerabilities
- They rarely guarantee that platforms' price oracles are tamper-proof

The audits do help but it is stated in the report that DeFi protocols must adopt a more robust approach to platform security.

Knowing these aspects, it is expected that these security risks will have an impact on the trust of the user due to the number of occurrences and total revenue stolen.

Impact of trust on a service

Cognitive trust is the ability and reliability of a customer to trust or be willing to rely on a service provider (Moorman et al., 1992; Rempel et al., 1985). Affective trust is the confidence one places in someone or a partner based on the degree of care and attention shown by the partner (Johnson-George and Swap, 1982; Rempel et al., 1985). It is characterized by a sense of security and perceived relationship strength. The study shows evidence that trust in financial services exchanges has cognitive and affective dimensions. These two dimensions are highly correlated, they are empirically distinguishable, and both dimensions of trust have unique antecedents. The results show that satisfaction with previous interactions contributes to cognitive trust, rather than emotional trust, suggesting that customer satisfaction in the financial services industry is largely based on core aspects of service delivery.

Furthermore, this study shows that a firm's reputation is positively related to customers' cognitive and affective trust in services. Although the study found a significant effect of emotional trust on a customer's willingness to meet with a service provider in the future, the study showed that emotional trust had little effect on financial services relationships. Researchers believe that trust facilitates relational processes that directly affect economic outcomes.

Survey results

A total of 33 survey responses were received. The surveys consist of 76% responders that are familiar with DeFi. Also 55% of responders have previously used a DEX. According to the survey, the most used DEX platforms are liquidity pool-based DEX's with 52% and order book-based DEXs with 24%.

In the surveys some security risks of DEX's are explained, 52% of respondents have been a victim of at least one of the security risks. The most common security risks are rug pulls 67% and pump and dump schemes 61%, see table 1. Based on a 5-point scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, respondents indicate that the security risk in DEX's negatively impact the use of DeFi with a mean of 2.9. Responders also indicate that the trust in DEX's negatively impact their use of DeFi with a mean of 3.5.

Table 1. Security risk

	Percentage
Rug Pulls	67%
Pump and dump schemes	61%
High-yield investment programs	50%
Smart Contract traps	28%
Smart contract exploits	28%

A high Cronbach's alpha is needed to represent the reliability of a variable. For a reliability variable a Cronbach's of 7.0 or higher is needed (Bland & Altman, 1997). With trust in DeFi as the dependent variable and trust in DEX as the independent variable Cronbach's alpha is 0.840. The relationship between the trust in DEX and DeFi is analyzed by using a simple linear regression in table 2.

Table 2. Simple Linear Regression

Slope	R	R ²	Significance
0.775	0.726	0.527	<0.001

With use of DEX's as the dependent variable and trust in DEX's as the independent variable Cronbach's alpha is 0.894. The relationship between the usage of DEX's and trust in DEX's is analyzed by using a simple linear regression in table 3.

Table 3. Simple Linear Regression

Slope	R	R ²	Significance
0.820	0.808	0.653	<0.001

DISCUSSION

According to the results, the security risks on the usage do have an impact on the trust of decentralized exchanges, and this then has a negative effect on the adoption of decentralized finance. As the world of decentralized finance grows leading to more decentralized exchanges, these exchanges must find a way to minimize the security risks to gain trust of users. The archival research done on trust in service providers, it shows that a firm reputation is positively related to customers' cognitive and affective trust in services. Furthermore, the study has found that trust has a significant effect on emotional trust on a customer's willingness to meet/interact with a service provider in the future. The survey results indicate that trust indeed has an impact on whether a service is used. Confirming H2, that trust in decentralized exchanges can influence the adoption of DeFi.

With trust in DeFi as the dependent variable and trust in DEX's as the independent variable, Cronbach's alpha of 0.840 indicates a high reliability of the variable. The model's coefficient of determination is 0.537, meaning 53.7% of the variation in use of DEX can be explained by the model. The correlation coefficient of 0.775 indicates a strong correlation between the variables. With a mean of 2.9, the responders say that the security risk in DEX's negatively impacts their use of DeFi. Further confirming H2, that trust in decentralized exchanges can influence the adoption of DeFi.

With use of DEX as the dependent variable and trust in DEX as the independent variable, Cronbach's alpha of 0.820 indicates a high reliability of the variable. The model's coefficient of determination is 0.653, meaning 65.3% of the variation in use of DEX can be explained by the model. The correlation coefficient of 0.808 indicates a strong correlation between the variables. Confirming H3, that the increase of security risks has a negative effect on the trust in decentralized exchanges.

The results from the survey indicate 52% of respondents have been a victim of at least one of the security risks that were presented, with rug pulls as the most common security risk with 67%. Rug pulls' account in scam revenue has significantly increased and scam revenue has increased by 81%. Considering that security risks impact the trust in DEX's and that trust can impact the adoption of DeFi it can be concluded that the increase in security risks impacts the adoption of DeFi. The surveys also state that the security risks on DEX negatively impact the use of DeFi.

Confirming H3, that the amount/increase of security risks on Decentralized exchange platforms has a negative effect on the adoption of decentralized finance.

Limitations

The research has its limitations with the first one being that the data from Chainanalysis includes variables that are not relevant to this research. The data consist of crypto crime that has also occurred on CEX's, which makes the data less valid. Next to this, the chain analysis report includes types of scams in their analysis that are not included in this research. This study also does not include the disadvantages of DEX's, which can define the usage of DEX's. To make the variables that measure trust more reliable and valid, prior research could have been used to quantify the variable.

CONCLUSION

This research has examined the impact of security risks in the DeFi sector with the focus on DEX's trust in DEX's and the overall adoption of DeFi. Previous studies have shown that these security risks are on the rise, with stolen funds due to smart contract vulnerabilities and scams being the most common of these security risks. To answer the research question:

“What is the impact of security risks on the trust of Decentralized exchanges, and how does this affect the adoption of Decentralized finance?”

Archival research and surveys have been conducted to measure the impact of these security risks on the trust in DEX's and the overall adoption of DeFi. The results and discussion have shown that the security risks have an impact on the trust of the users. It has been discovered that these security risks impact their use of DeFi and DEX's in particular. With users avoiding DeFi it can be concluded that the security risks and the lack of trust in DEX's do influence the overall adoption of DeFi. Although it is important to state that DEX's do not influence the rate of scams in the DeFi space. It has become clear that there are several reasons why DEX's are avoided and not used. To increase the reliability and validity of this research it is recommended to consider these reasons. This research can be used to improve the security and awareness of DeFi protocols, in particular DEX's to make DeFi more digital resilient.

Further research

This research is conducted on the impact of trust in DEX's on the overall adoption of DeFi,

taking scams and stolen funds due to smart contract vulnerabilities into account. Further research should look into other aspects that have an influence on the adoption of DeFi (e.g., lack of regulation, lack of liquidity in DEX's). Since this research is conducted in a short time window there are only 33 surveys conducted. Due to the small scale of the surveys, the findings cannot be applied to a broad population. The surveys can be extended and possibly supported by interviewing several experts in the field of DeFi. Furthermore, further research should focus on the several other security risks in the DeFi ecosystem (e.g., Ransomware, Malware, Money laundering, Terrorism Financing, Darknet Markets) and how these risks impact the adoption of DeFi.

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